

The Formation Sites of Massive Young Star Clusters

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Star clusters are central to our understanding of cosmic history. They are the formation sites of a large fraction, if not most, of the stars in the Universe. The surviving bound clusters allow us to trace the dynamical and chemical enrichment histories of galaxies, including the Milky Way. Moreover, because of their luminosities, they can be observed in galaxies well beyond the Local Group. Yet despite their importance, surprisingly little is known about the detailed formation of star clusters and their early evolution. This is particularly true for massive clusters (those $\sim 10^4 M_{\odot}$ and above).

Part of the reason for our limited knowledge has been the lack of newly forming massive star cluster candidates. They are difficult to find because massive clusters are much less common than lower-mass star-forming regions; statistically, this means they are relatively more distant. They are also expected to be associated with large amounts of molecular gas and obscuring dust, making them difficult to detect optically. Near-infrared observations help, but it is hard to identify the youngest regions without broader wavelength coverage. A different approach is to search for signs of infall onto molecular clumps and/or regions where the embedded newly formed stars are heating the dust and gas still associated with the cluster.

Surveys at millimeter and far-infrared wavelengths have been successful in identifying regions that could be forming massive clusters (e.g., [1], [2]) in the Milky Way and the Magellanic Clouds. However, little is directly known about the stellar content from those wavelengths. Instead one has to turn to the near-infrared for the identified clusters. Further, owing to the distance of the massive star-forming regions, one needs both good sensitivity and high spatial

resolution to reach the lowest possible stellar masses within the clusters.

One particularly exciting region discovered in the Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC) is the brightest far-infrared source in the HERITAGE survey [3] conducted with the *Herschel Space Observatory*. This bright source lies within the LMC's N79 star-forming complex, and we refer to it here as H72.97-69.39. Estimating the star formation rate in this region from other infrared-identified young stellar clusters in the N79 complex suggests that the rate has increased over the last few million years. Further, H72.97-69.39 may be an analogue, in the early stages of formation, of the well-known, extremely massive R136 cluster at the center of the 30 Doradus region [2]. However, the Herschel data do not have the spatial resolution to resolve structure below ~ 1 parsec in the LMC, and this is insufficient to resolve the dense inner regions of massive star clusters.

The multi-conjugate adaptive optics system at Gemini South, known as GeMS, coupled with the near-infrared Gemini South Adaptive Optics Imager (GSAOI), are well suited for resolving the inner structure of star clusters at the distance of the LMC. With this system, we can probe the nature of this exciting system, potentially revealing a massive star cluster in the making. The Figure shows the region around H72.97-69.39 as seen with GeMS/GSAOI in the H and K_s bandpasses.

The color-magnitude diagram shows that the cluster is deeply embedded, with extinction measures in K_s of ~ 1.5 mag or more (> 15 mag of extinction in the V band). Based on our GeMS/GSAOI photometry, the total stellar mass for the cluster is at least $10^4 M_{\odot}$ after extrapolating the high-mass

Left: The central part of the GeMS/GSAOI H and K_s band image of the forming cluster H72.97-69.39. The stretch is logarithmic to show a large dynamic range. *Right:* The $H-K$ versus H color-magnitude diagram for H72.97-69.39. The red dots are stars within the field shown at left, the black points are all stars detected across the full $\sim 90''$ GeMS/GSAOI field, and cyan shows stars in a control region well away from H72.97-69.39. The line is a 1-Myr isochrone from [5]. The cluster is deeply embedded in the material from which it is forming, and there are indications of additional dust lanes that could be adding more material to the cluster. (Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/M. Andersen)

data over the full mass function. However, as the large amount of extinction suggests, there is a substantial amount of molecular material still present within the cluster, providing the potential for further star formation. From the measured extinction and the additional dense gas detected by the Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array (ALMA) [4], we estimate that the total amount of molecular gas remaining is more than $5000 M_{\odot}$.

Although not as massive as R136, H72.97-69.39 is a compelling case of a massive cluster caught at a very early stage of its life. In the coming years we expect to learn substantially more about this cluster through deep observations from space and the ground. Studying systems

like this in detail requires a coordinated multi-facility effort. This includes high spatial resolution near-infrared imaging and spectroscopy to reveal the stellar content, far-infrared observations for the initial identification and current star formation, and data at millimeter wavelengths to probe the molecular gas still within these clusters, which provides the fuel for further growth.

References

- [1] Barnes, P. J., et al. 2010, *MNRAS*, 402, 73
- [2] Ochsendorf, B. B., et al. 2017, *NatAs*, 1, 784
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- [4] Nayak, O., et al. 2019, *ApJ*, 877, 135
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